

concentration solutions of 7 insecticidal formulations were applied as foliar spray on egg masses. Distilled water and no treatment were the controls. Em masses were observed daily for 10 d.

Monocrotophos 36 WSC was most effective in killing newly emerged YSB larvae, followed by fenitrothion 50 EC and chlorpyrifos 20 EC (see table). □

Preference, oviposition response, and population growth of *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) on selected rice varieties

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Several rice varieties with resistance to thrips have been identified by mass screening at IIRRI. We compared thrips' preference, oviposition response, and population increase on varieties BJI, TKM6, ASD7, Dahanala 2220 (resistant check), and Nira (susceptible check).

Preference test. Pregerminated seeds of each variety were sown singly near the periphery of 30-cm-diam clay pots filled with paddy soil, with 10 pots/variety. At the first true-leaf stage, a small glass vial containing 10-cm-long rice leaf cuts with 100 thrips adults was placed in the middle of each pot, which was covered with a snug-fitting mylar cage. Thrips settling on each seedling were recorded at 1, 4, 16, 32, and 48 h after release.

Oviposition response. Five- to seven-day-old seedlings with roots wrapped in moist cotton were placed singly in 20 by 2.5 cm glass test tubes (5 tubes/variety) and infested with 5 pairs of newly emerged males and females. The adults were removed after 2 d and the eggs laid on each seedling counted.

Population increase. Three-week-old rice seedlings (5 seedlings/15-cm-diam pot) were infested with 25 pairs of newly emerged male and female thrips and the pots covered with a mylar cage. Thrips eggs, larvae, prepupae, pupae, and adults in each cage were counted 14 d after infestation.

In the preference test, thrips adults discriminated between susceptible and

Table 1. Percent of *S. biformis* adults that settled on seedlings of resistant and susceptible rice varieties 1, 4, 16, 32, and 48 h after infestation (HI) in a free-choice test. ^a IIRRI, 1987.

Variety	IRRI acc. no.	Adults (%) that settled on seedlings				
		1 HI	4 HI	16 HI	32 HI	48 HI
Dahanala (resistant check)	50330	3.2 c	0.9 e	0.9 d	1.8 d	3.5 c
BJI	256	34.2 a	27.8 b	25.3 b	22.8 b	21.5 b
TKM6	237	10.3 c	13.7 d	15.8 c	16.4 c	17.5 b
ASD7	6303	20.3 b	21.2 c	20.9 bc	17.5 c	19.7 b
Nira (susceptible check)	6309	25.3 b	35.9 a	36.8 a	40.7 a	36.1 a

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Av of 10 replications, 100 adults/pot.

resistant varieties soon after release (Table 1). At 1 h after release, significantly more adults had settled on susceptible Nira than on resistant Dahanala 2220. After 4 h or longer, significantly more adults were on Nira than on seedlings of other varieties; Dahanala 2220 was the least preferred.

Dahanala 2220 and TKM6 were the least preferred for oviposition; Nira was most preferred (Table 2). The population increase was highest on Nira and lowest on Dahanala 2220. Factors affecting resistance or susceptibility of rice varieties to thrips are being investigated. □

Table 2. Oviposition response and population increase of *S. biformis* on plants of resistant and susceptible rice varieties. ^a IIRRI, 1987.

Variety	Eggs laid (no./5 females) in 48 h	Thrips ^b (no.) at 14 d after infestation
Dahanala 2220 (resistant check)	0.3 d	0.2 d
BJI	1.2 c	17.2 b
TKM6	0.5 d	9.2 c
ASD7	2.1 b	18.2 b
Nira (susceptible check)	4.9 a	90.6 a

^a In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. Av of 5 replications. ^b From 25 pairs of males and females.

Ovicidal activity of insecticides against yellow stem borer (YSB)

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YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Wlk.) is an internal rice borer pest. Satisfactory control can be achieved by spraying a persistent insecticide with ovicidal activity. We laboratory-tested 7 insecticides — monocrotophos, fenitrothion, cypermethrin, carbaryl, chlorpyrifos, diazinon, and methyl parathion — at 0.04% concentration for their ovicidal activity against YSB.

YSB egg masses collected from ricefields were sprayed with aqueous solutions of insecticide. Control 1 was sprayed with distilled water and control 2 was untreated. The experiment was replicated three times.

Ovicidal activity of insecticides at 0.04% concentration against YSB. ^a Gujarat, India.

Insecticide	Unhatched eggs ^a (%)
Monocrotophos	63.2
Fenitrothion	33.4
Cypermethrin	15.6
Carbaryl	11.5
Chlorpyrifos	61.7
Diazinon	26.9
Methyl parathion	60.3
Control 1 (water spray)	8.1
Control 2 (no treatment)	6.0
CD (0.05)	0.5

^a Av of 3 replications. Data were converted to angular values.

Both treated and untreated egg masses were placed in petri dishes lined with moistened filter paper and observed daily for 7 d. Highest ovicidal activity was with monocrotophos, followed by chlorpyrifos and methyl parathion (see table). □